

IMPROVEMENT OF THE LEXICAL COMPETENCE OF PEDAGOGUES BASED ON AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH AS AN URGENT PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *This article deals with problems of teaching foreign languages in professional development system. Today, the reform and improvement of the continuous education system of our country, which is on the path of the third Renaissance development, raising it to a new level of quality, introducing advanced pedagogical and information technologies to it.*

Keywords: *foreign languages, competence, integrated skills, lexicology, self-development, professional development.*

The future and prospects of every society are determined by the level of development of the education system, which is an integral part of it and a vital necessity. Today, the reform and improvement of the continuous education system of our country, which is on the path of the third Renaissance development, raising it to a new level of quality, introducing advanced pedagogical and information technologies to it, and increasing the effectiveness of education has risen to the level of state policy.

In recent years, in the education system of our republic, researches are being conducted on the issues of improving the educational system based on innovative technologies, strengthening its national ground, raising the training of socially active and qualified competitive personnel to the level of world standards. As Kh.Manzarov pointed out, quality changes and high efficiency in the field of education are reflected in their compatibility with world educational requirements and the extent to which the competences acquired by pedagogues in their future work activities are put into practice. That is, reforms in the field of education ensure the quality and efficiency of education and create a process of pedagogical innovation.

Modernizing the educational process in higher education institutions, developing the professional competence of teachers in improving the quality of the personnel training system, arming them with modern professional knowledge, qualifications and skills in the field, independently and creatively using scientific and technical innovations and development of skills to solve prospective tasks is considered one of the important tasks. Because globalization and rapid development of science and technology require rapid adaptation of specialists to modern requirements and professional innovations. This, in turn, forms a responsible attitude to one of the types of continuous education - the improvement of personnel qualifications and their retraining.

Also, in order to constantly improve the quality of education and to raise it to the level of world standards, it is important to improve the qualifications of leaders, officials, and professors.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 27, 2019 “On the introduction of the system of continuous professional development of managers and pedagogues of higher educational institutions” No. PD-5789 [1] and the Resolution of Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated from September 23, 2019 “To ensure the implementation” No. 797 [2] introduces mechanisms for continuous updating of professional knowledge, skills and

abilities of managers and pedagogues of higher education institutions, to ensure the quality of higher education in accordance with modern requirements to increase professional training to the necessary level, to ensure the implementation of direct and indirect forms of retraining and professional development based on the principles of variation and complementing each other introduction of updating mechanisms, increasing professional training to the level necessary to ensure the quality of higher education in accordance with modern requirements;

to ensure and monitor the full implementation of direct, remote, alternative and indirect forms of professional training;

independent selection and mastering of the forms of continuous professional development aimed at satisfying professional needs of leaders and pedagogues based on their scientific and pedagogical potential;

a number of tasks are presented, such as improving the qualification requirements for the quality of training of managers and pedagogues by ensuring the integration of education, science and production. Therefore, the reforms in the field of education, the development of information and digital technologies and their introduction into the educational system require the pedagogue to be mobile, flexible, competent and keep up with the times.

Also, in order to consistently improve the quality of education and to raise it to the level of world standards, it is important to improve the skills of leaders, officials, and professors.

Significant changes are taking place in the education system of Uzbekistan. From this point of view, we started researching pedagogical problems within the topic by studying literature. During the research, the process of studying the literature made it possible to find out which aspects of the pedagogical problems of improving the lexical competence of pedagogues have been well resolved, and which issues have not been resolved.

While studying the issue of improving the lexical competence of pedagogues, let's talk in detail about lexicology, which occupies an important place in linguistics. Professor N. Chomsky of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology describes lexicology as a layer in linguistics that deals with the study of the vocabulary of the language. The science of lexicology is "change of word meaning", i.e. expansion and narrowing of word meaning, types of words according to the form of use and meaning relations, their territorial and social strata, new words includes a number of issues such as their occurrence. As noted by A. Abduazizov sections such as semasiology, lexicography, onomasiology, etymology, phraseology, onomastics are components of lexicology. Lexicology develops the laws of practical use and development of the vocabulary, the principles of methodological classification of words. It also analyzes the standards of use in colloquial and literary languages, professionalism, dialectism, archaism, neologism, standardization of lexicalized word combinations and draws certain conclusions about them. According to I.V. Arnold [3], the collection of all words and phrases in the language is the lexicon. Therefore, when the lexicon is viewed as a specific system, it is assumed that the meanings of words and concepts are interrelated.

Above, the concept of lexicon, i.e. word units, was clarified. In this section, we consider the lexical competence of pedagogues as an actual pedagogical problem. Today, the competence approach to the process of teaching foreign languages is widely applied. We found it necessary to clarify the concepts of competence and competency when covering the section.

Competence is a broad concept, its content and essence are interpreted differently by scientists. Many interpretations of the terms "competence" and "competency" have been given in

foreign studies. For example, R. Jackendoff says that “competence means knowledge in this or that field”. “Competence” (from the Latin *compete*-achieve, match, match) means the authority given to a specific organization or a person in a position by a law, statute or other document.

J. Winterton and D. Delamare-Le competence is the standard behavior required by a certain activity, behavior, and competence is the level of compliance with this requirement (standard), that is, the final result of demonstrating competence, - are described as.

A. Verbisky and O. Iskanderova said that “competence” is his goals, values, motives, personal qualities, knowledge, skills, qualifications, abilities and experiences that ensure the implementation of this or that activity by a person system; and competence is defined as the level of mastery of practical activity technologies and the development of social and moral qualities of a person manifested and realized in practice, defined by A.S. Belkin defined competence as professional authority and functions that create necessary conditions for effective activity in the educational process, and competence as a set of professional and personal qualities that ensure effective implementation of competence.

This concept entered the educational system of our republic in the early 1990s. By experts, it is named differently, for example, by J. Jalolov, and T. Sattorov by concepts such as “factoriality”, “skill” in the sources reflecting the theory and history of pedagogy. Below are the definitions given by the scientists of our country.

In linguistics, the term “competence” was introduced by the American scientist N. Chomsky in the middle of the 20th century, and the term “language competence” is the term “language use” used in a semantically opposite sense.

But for the first time this term is defined as being used by Scottish scientist J. Raven in 1590 in Webster’s Online Dictionary (“Competence” was first used in popular English literature: sometime before 1590).

The difference between these terms was the level of the “speaker’s and the listener’s” knowledge of the language and its practical application, i.e., speech activity. By the 70s of the last century, it was used by N. Chomsky’s followers as the concepts of potential knowledge of the language and the knowledge of the language of the real speaker, that is, language competence, and its use in real speech in any authentic situations, that is, “language activity”. D. Slobin and D. Green gave a clear explanation of the content of these concepts and they emphasized that “a person can communicate in practice, that is, in any specific situation, only if he has the ability to speak and understand theoretically”. In a short period of time, these views caused the emergence of the concept of “competence” over time, that is, in connection with development. This, in turn, caused the emergence of the terms “lexical competence”, “strategic competence”, “discourse competence”, “communicative competence”. Over time, in addition to these, the concept of “competencies” appeared.

The term “competence” was adopted in 1996 in Strasbourg with the Council of Europe as part of the research on teaching in the scope of communicatively oriented education to determine the level of foreign language acquisition in relation to foreign languages. At that time, “competence” was defined as the ability to perform some activity based on the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in training.

J. Jalolov [5] defined “Competence” as trying to learn a language, being able to learn a language.

G.Selevko gives the following description of competence: "...competency consists of knowledge, skills and abilities formed as a result of language education, it represents the integral characteristics of a person".

Today, the word competence means ability, competent ability, and competence and competence in education are education aimed at forming the ability to apply acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications in personal, professional and social activities. is understood. The competence approach in language education is the ability of learners to use the language materials they learn and the information they receive in their life activities, to express their thoughts in this language independently orally and in writing, and to use lexical units in accordance with speech situations. It consists in forming the ability to use the language in a purposeful and practical way.

From this point of view, one of the indicators of the quality of education is competence. Competence is not only a set of knowledge and skills, but is characterized by the ability to mobilize the acquired knowledge and apply it in practice in specific situations.

In order for a person to be able to engage in personal, social, economic and professional relationships, to take his place in society, to solve the problems he faces, to have a broad outlook and knowledge in all aspects, first of all, it is necessary to integrate the teaching of subjects, study in society and in order to engage in mutual communication, it is necessary to master a foreign language perfectly and to improve the competence of being able to use it effectively in communication.

According to the "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan": "competence (lot.competo - I achieve, I am worthy) means a law, regulation or other document of a certain state body (local self-government body) or an official. scope of powers, rights and duties defined by; it means knowledge and experience in one or another field". Summarizing, taking into account the above descriptions, competence is a set of various interrelated abilities and characteristics of a person, necessary for effective work in a certain field.

In the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" this term is also defined as follows: "competence (Latin competere - capable, to be worthy) the range of powers of a certain body or official defined in official documents, authority; is a person's awareness of a certain area, the level of knowledge of this area". Competence is the manifestation of an algorithm that ensures effectiveness through human capabilities, and the goal-oriented action of a person as a specialist that fully demonstrates his capabilities.

According to B.Kh.Khodjaev, competence is the ability to use acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in everyday and professional activities.

According to K.J.Riskulova, "competency" means a set of professional laws, principles, requirements, rules, duties, tasks and obligations, as well as personal deontological norms, necessary for the owner of this or that profession. Competence is related to a person's practical activity, and it is the ability to demonstrate competence norms in work experience based on creativity based on the requirements of society. The main criterion of competence is determined by effective activity, training of competitive personnel.

In contrast to the systematization of the results of a person's cognitive activity, knowledge that exists in the form of concepts and ideas, competence is determined only in practice. In general, competence is the practical application of existing knowledge, skills, and abilities, the ability to provide missing knowledge, and the necessary knowledge, skills, and abilities that are characterized by the manifestation of one's capabilities.

The following traditional classifications of competence are noted in the scientific and methodical literature:

- political and social competences related to the ability to take responsibility, participate in cooperative decision-making;
- oriented towards living with other people regardless of their culture, language and religion, understanding them, helping them and eliminating mutual disagreements, total competencies encountered in the life of a horse;
- competences that determine the ownership of written and oral communication, which are important in professional activity and community life;
- competencies related to the emergence of the information society (acquiring new technologies and determining their advantages and disadvantages).

Based on this, the educational process is divided into two main types of competencies: basic and private competencies. Basic competences are the ability to engage in personal, social, economic and professional relationships, to take one's place in society, to solve problems, and most importantly, to be competitive in one's field and profession. focused on the formation of qualifications. They are divided into the following types: competences such as communicative, working with information, self-development as a person, socially active citizenship, general cultural, mathematical literacy.

Professor N. Muslimov [6] expresses the opinion that private competence is a competence related to the field in the process of mastering each academic subject in education, based on its specificity and content of the subject. In particular, learning English requires the formation of speech, linguistic, lexical, socio-cultural or discourse and strategic competencies in language learners.

It should be noted that basic and private competencies are inextricably linked, and they will produce effective results only if they are formed while complementing each other.

In the conditions of intense globalization and market relations, resistance to strong competition, which takes priority in the labor market, requires every specialist to have professional competence and to improve it consistently. If we have discussed the essence of the concept of “competence” above, now it is the turn of the concept of “competence”. In the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, the term competence is derived from the Latin word “compete” and is defined as “I achieve”, “I am worthy”, and according to A.Belkin, it means means having awareness, knowledge and experience in the field. In particular, G.Garfinkel understands competence as a person’s knowledge, skills and experiences, social-professional, that is, compatibility with the professional position he occupies in society, ability to perform his duties and solve related problems. From his opinion in this regard, competence is assumed to be a persons possession of certain knowledge and skills and effective work in this or that situation.

In summarize the model of the formation and development of lexical competence is the basis for many studies in the world of science. As the lexical reserve of foreign language learners expands and their vocabulary increases, so does their ability to speak a foreign language.

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